

APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH LITERATURE IN CIS COUNTRIES

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Abstract. This study explores modern approaches to teaching English through literature in the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries. It highlights the role of literary texts in developing linguistic, cultural, and critical thinking skills. The study analyzes communicative, reader-response, and intercultural approaches and evaluates their effectiveness in the CIS educational context. The findings suggest that integrating literature into English language teaching enhances learners' motivation and intercultural competence.

Key words: teaching English, literature, communicative approach, reader-response approach, intercultural competence, language education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot Mustaqil Davlatlar Hamdo'stligi (MDH) mamlakatlarida adabiyot orqali ingliz tilini o'qitishning zamonaviy yondashuvlarini o'rganadi. Unda badiiy matnlarning lisoniy, madaniy va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ, kitobxon-reaksiya (reader-response) va madaniyatlararo yondashuvlar tahlil qilinadi hamda ularning MDH ta'lim tizimidagi samaradorligi baholanadi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, adabiyotni ingliz tili o'qitish jarayoniga integratsiya qilish o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini va madaniyatlararo kompetensiyasini oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tilini o'qitish, adabiyot, kommunikativ yondashuv, kitobxon-reaksiya yondashuvi, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, til ta'limi.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании рассматриваются современные подходы к преподаванию английского языка через литературу в странах Содружества Независимых Государств (СНГ). Особое внимание уделяется роли литературных текстов в развитии лингвистических, культурных навыков и навыков критического мышления. В работе анализируются коммуникативный подход, подход «читательской реакции» (reader-response) и межкультурный подход, а также оценивается их эффективность в образовательном контексте стран СНГ. Результаты исследования показывают, что интеграция литературы в преподавание английского языка повышает мотивацию учащихся и их межкультурную компетенцию.

Ключевые слова: преподавание английского языка, литература, коммуникативный подход, подход читательской реакции, межкультурная компетенция, языковое образование.

Introduction

The use of literature in teaching foreign languages has drawn more attention in recent years. More interactive and student-centered techniques are progressively replacing conventional methods in CIS nationals that mostly focus on grammar and translation. Students who study English via literature acquire critical thinking abilities and cultural understanding in addition to language ability. Students are exposed to real-life situations, a variety of viewpoints, and realistic language through literary literature.

According to Lazar [5], literature in language teaching helps develop interpretative abilities and emotional engagement. Similarly, Paran [6], emphasizes that literature enhances both language proficiency and personal development.

This study is relevant because English teaching methods in CIS nations need to be updated and adjusted to meet international educational standards.

This article's goal is to examine important methods of teaching English via literature and how CIS educational systems use them.

Materials and Methods

The research is based on theoretical analysis of contemporary studies in language teaching and literary pedagogy. The study applies descriptive and comparative analysis methods to examine major approaches to teaching.

Key sources include works by Lazar [5], Paran [6], Hall [4], and Carter & Long [2].

Results:

The analysis identifies several effective approaches to teaching English through literature in CIS countries:

1. Communicative Approach

This strategy emphasizes the use of literature as a communication medium. Students participate in group activities, debate literature, and voice their viewpoints, promotes conversation and engagement builds confidence and fluency by encourages active involvement.

Literary writings stop being only objects of analysis and start acting as a medium of communication.

2. Reader-Response Approach

Students' individual interpretations of literary works are highlighted via the reader-response method. With this method students relate books to their personal lives. Multiple interpretations are encouraged and its fosters critical and imaginative thinking

This method makes learning more interesting and meaningful, claims Hall [4].

3. Language-Based Approach

This method focuses on linguistic features of literary texts such as :
vocabulary development, grammar in context, stylistic analysis

It is especially useful in CIS countries where students need strong language foundations.

4. Intercultural Approach

Literature introduces learners to different cultures and worldviews. It is beneficial for enhancing intercultural competence, to reduce cultural stereotypes and it promotes global awareness

This is particularly important in the context of globalization and international communication.

5. Integrated Approach

This method considered to be the modern one especially in teaching its often combines several approaches.

First, it combines language learning + cultural understanding. Then it uses literature for multiple purposes. Also it considered to be more flexible and effective.

Teachers in CIS countries increasingly adopt this approach to meet diverse student needs.

Discussion

The results demonstrate the substantial advantages of teaching English via literature in the context of CIS education.

Firstly, it increases student motivation. Literary texts are more engaging than traditional exercises.

Second, it fosters the development of higher-order cognitive abilities including assessment, interpretation, and analysis.

But there are still a number of difficulties for example: Lack of modern teaching materials, limited teacher training, over-reliance on traditional methods.

Despite these challenges, the integration of literature into English teaching is becoming more widespread in CIS countries.

Teachers play a crucial role in selecting appropriate texts and designing interactive activities

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has explored different approaches to teaching English through literature in CIS countries.

The results demonstrate that literature is a powerful tool for developing language skills, cultural awareness, and critical thinking.

Modern approaches such as communicative, reader-response, and intercultural methods significantly improve the effectiveness of English language teaching.

It can be concluded that integrating literature into language education is essential for preparing students for real-life communication and global interaction.

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